

Event metadata

Event title	WORKSHOP: Nextflow for the life sciences
Event type	Workshop
Date of event	22 - 23 July 2025
Time of event	1-5pm AEST
Topic description	<p>The rise of big data has made it essential to be able to analyse and perform experiments on large datasets in a portable and reproducible manner. Nextflow is a popular bioinformatics workflow orchestrator that makes it easy to run data-intensive computational pipelines. It enables scalable and reproducible scientific workflows using software containers on any infrastructure. It allows the adaptation of workflows written in most languages and provides the ability to customise and optimise workflows for different computational environments, types and sizes of data.</p> <p>Learn to build reproducible and scalable scientific workflows with Nextflow in this two-part workshop. Part one covers the fundamental principles of Nextflow pipeline development using the “Hello Nextflow” materials. Part two offers practical, hands-on experience creating a multi-sample Nextflow workflow for RNAseq data preparation.</p>
Format description	<p>This workshop took place over two sessions via a distributed training methodology.</p> <p>Participants joined in person satellite sites at host universities and research institutes across Australia which connected via Zoom with lead trainers Fred Jaya and Michael Geaghan. All sites were supported by experienced local facilitators, who guided participants through hands-on activities and helped them put their new skills into action.</p> <p>Satellite sites were located in central locations in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brisbane • Sydney • Perth • Adelaide • Melbourne • Canberra <p>If travel was an impediment to participating, alternative options were provided.</p> <p>A shared Google Doc was used to answer questions as they arose, troubleshoot code and share tips and resources.</p>

	<p>Participation was free but subject to application with selection.</p> <p>Applications were reviewed by the organising committee.</p> <p>Number of participants = 61</p>
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/nextflow-life-sciences
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	<p>Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091</p> <p>Workflows http://edamontology.org/topic_0769</p>
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This is an intermediate-advanced workshop for people developing reproducible bioinformatics workflows.
Prerequisites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You must be associated with an Australian organisation for your application to be considered • Command line / linux skills are essential. The workshop will be conducted in a Unix environment. • Experience developing reproducible workflows (e.g. bash, CWL, WDL, or Snakemake) • Experience with Github and a Github account
Technical requirements	<p>Online Platform</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A shared Google Doc was used to facilitate questions and troubleshooting and interaction with the Trainers. <p>Participants required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Laptop with VSCode installed • Access to the internet <p>Virtual Machines</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants were provided with access to virtual machines running on NCI Nirin Cloud. Packages, workflows and data were preinstalled.
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of the workshop you should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe and use core Nextflow components sufficient to build a simple multi-step workflow • Describe next-step concepts such as operations and channels

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch a Nextflow workflow locally • Find and interpret outputs and log files generated by Nextflow • Troubleshoot basic issues • Develop a scalable workflow that processes multiple samples and incorporates advanced features • Assess the effectiveness of a workflow in handling multiple samples in parallel execution
Lead Trainers	<p>Fred Jaya, Senior Bioinformatician (Australian BioCommons), Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney.</p> <p>Dr Michael Geaghan, Senior Bioinformatician (Australian BioCommons), Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney.</p>
Facilitators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brisbane: Magdalena Antczak (Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation (QCIF)) and Marie-Emilie Gauthier (Queensland University of Technology (QUT)) • Perth: Sarah Beecroft and Pratihba Raghunandan (Pawsey Supercomputing Centre) • Canberra: Kisanu Liyanage (National Computational Infrastructure (NCI)) • Adelaide: John Salamon and Michael Roach (South Australian Genomics Centre (SAGC)) • Melbourne: Emma Gail and Grace Hall (Melbourne Bioinformatics), Richard Lupat (Peter MacCallum Cancer Centre) • Sydney: Thanh Nguyen, Eric Urng, Matthew Hobbs (Garvan Institute of Medical Research)
Training materials	<p>The materials were developed by the Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney. The workshop was enabled through the Australian BioCommons - BioCLI Platforms Project (NCRIS via Bioplatforms Australia).</p> <p>Training materials webpage: https://sydney-informatics-hub.github.io/hello-nextflow-2025/</p>
Related work	<p>These materials build Seqera's Hello Nextflow materials: https://training.nextflow.io/hello_nextflow/</p>